

Relationship between weed dry weight and rice grain yield under upland condition. Parwanipur, India, 1988.

yield per unit increase in dry weed weight to be between 0.48% (1.4206 g/m²) and 0.23% (0.6929 g/m²), at 99% level of confidence.

The equation developed here could be used to assess yield loss caused by weeds in upland ricefields under conditions similar to those in Parwanipur. □

6% broadleaved weeds.

Of the herbicides and cultural treatments tested, thiobencarb at 1.5 kg ai/ha followed by one hand weeding at

25-30 d after sowing (DAS) gave the highest yield and net return (see table). Results with butachlor at the same rate and weeding schedule were similar. □

Weed control in direct sown rice cultivar (MW10) under rainfed upland conditions of Chhattisgarh, MP, India, 1984-86.^a

Treatment	Formulation	Rate applied (kg ai/ha)	Yield (t/ha)				Gross return (\$)	Cost of treatment (\$)	Net return (\$)
			1984	1985	1986	Mean			
Thiobencarb (saturon)	50 EC	2.0	3.5	1.2	0.8	1.8	185	25	160
Thiobencarb plus one hand weeding at 25-30 DAS	50 EC	1.5	3.7	2.8	2.2	2.9	288	35	253
Butachlor (Delchlor)	50 EC	2.0	2.9	1.0	1.0	1.6	164	26	138
Butachlor with one hand weeding at 25-30 DAS	50 EC	1.5	3.1	3.4	2.0	2.8	285	40	247
Butachlor (Machete)	50 EC	2.0	2.6	0.7	1.0	1.4	141	25	116
Butachlor with one hand weeding at 25-30 DAS	50 EC	1.5	2.7	2.8	2.0	2.5	251	40	211
Pendimethalin	30 EC	1.5	2.4	0.8	0.8	1.4	138	30	108
Hand weeding twice at 20 and 40 DAS			3.4	3.00	1.7	2.7	271	47	224
Weed-free check			3.2	3.1	2.4	2.9	290	67	223
Nonweeded control			1.3	0.8	0.4	0.8	83	00	83
Experiment mean			2.9	2.0	1.6	2.2			
LSD (0.05)			0.5	0.10	0.5				

^aRice \$100.00/t, thiobencarb \$6.00/liter, Delchlor \$6.34/liter, Machete \$6.34/liter, pendimethalin \$5.93, labor charges \$0.67/d, labor required for 2 weedings (40 + 30 DAS) and for weed-free check (40 + 30 + 20 + 10 DAS) in man-days/ha.

Water management

Weed control in direct seeded rice under upland conditions of Chhattisgarh, India

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We evaluated herbicides for effective and economical control of weeds in direct seeded rice under upland conditions. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with four replications. MW10 was the test variety.

The dominant weeds were *Echinochloa colona*, *Cyperus rotundus*, *Setaria glauca*, *Cynodon dactylon*, *Eclipta alba*, *Alternanthera* spp., and *Commelina* spp. The weed population included 65% grasses, 29% sedges, and

Effect of submergence depth on rice yield and water percolation and nitrogen leaching in sandy clay loam soils

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We measured the effect of different submergence depths on rice yield, water percolation, and nitrogen leaching in the sandy clay loam (Typic Haplustalf) soils of Thanjavur District. The experimental field had neutral soil reaction and low organic matter content (0.51%). Soil had 20% clay, 3% silt, 13% coarse sand, 63% fine sand with low CEC (9.7 meq/100 g) and exchangeable bases.

The experiment was repeated in two seasons--kharif (Jun-Oct) and rabi

(Oct-Jan)--for 3 yr (1985-87). Water depths were 2.5, 5.0, and 7.5 cm, maintained by irrigating the 6- × 5-m plots daily.

Loss of water to percolation was measured in 20-cm-diameter, 30-cm-high metal rings covered by polythene sheets. Percolation loss was measured daily from 8 d after planting to 15 d before harvest.

Leachate collected daily after basal and topdressed prilled urea was analyzed for ammoniacal N using magnesium oxide and for nitrate N using Devarda alloy. Nitrogen loss by leaching was quantified from N concentration in the leachate and amount of water lost by percolation.

Daily topping with 2.5 or 5.0 cm water significantly increased yield compared to 7.5 cm water depth during the dry season. Percolation loss increased with depth of submergence

during both wet and dry seasons, but dry season rates were only about 50% of those in the wet season. This may be due to a rise in groundwater table during the monsoon period. Initial concentrations of ammoniacal and nitrate N were high, gradually dropping within 15 d after application of N (see table). N loss increased with increasing water depth. N loss in the dry season was about 50% of loss in the wet season. □

Effect of submergence depth on rice yield and loss of water and N.^a Thanjavur, India, 1985-87 wet and dry seasons.

Water depth (cm)	Wet season				Dry season			
	Grain yield (t/ha)	Water loss (mm)	N loss (kg/ha)		Grain yield (t/ha)	Water loss (mm)	N loss (kg/ha)	
			NH ₄ ⁺	NO ₃ ⁻			NH ₄ ⁺	NO ₃ ⁻
2.5	6.4	373	4.6	1.3	4.6	196	2.2	0.6
5.0	6.6	448	5.5	1.6	4.7	238	2.7	0.8
7.5	6.2	516	6.2	1.8	4.4	265	3.0	0.9
LSD (0.05)	ns				0.1			

^aAv for 3 yr.

Effect of irrigation schedule on grain yield and water use efficiency in transplanted rice

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Five levels of irrigation (see table) were laid out in randomized block design with four replications.

Soil of the experimental field was sandy loam, pH 6.8, EC 0.28 dS/m, 0.58% organic C, with 185, 18, and 250 kg available N, P, and K/ha. Test variety was IR36.

Water applied 1 or 3 d after

Effect of irrigation schedule on rice grain yield, water requirement, and water use efficiency. Ambikapur, India, 1987 wet season.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)	Effective rainfall (cm)	Water requirement (cm)	Water use efficiency (kg/ha per cm)
Continuous submergence 5 ± 2 cm water (CS)	3.7	36	126	29
Application of 7 cm water 1 DAD	3.7	43	113	32
Application of 7 cm water 3 DAD	3.5	46	88	40
Application of 7 cm water 5 DAD	3.4	47	82	41
Rainfed with provision to store all rainwater (RF)	3.1	74	74	42
LSD (0.05)	0.2			

disappearance of ponded water (DAD) was as good as continuous submergence (CS) in grain yield and

significantly superior to rainfed (RF). Irrigation 3 DAD saved 38 cm water without sacrificing yield. □

Farm machinery

A root zone liquid urea applicator for wetland rice

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A simple root zone liquid applicator attachment to the hand compression insecticide sprayer was developed in 1984 (see figure). Prilled urea dissolved in water (1:2 ratio) is kept under pressure in the sprayer tank. The applicator is attached in place of the insecticide lance rod using an adaptor pipe with matching threads.

The operator lifts the applicator with the right hand and gently pushes the lower ends of eight branch nozzles

Urea solution application using root zone liquid applicator attachment to hand compression sprayer. AP, India, 1984-1986.